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A New 'Trajanic' Sestertius from Somerset and its Context:
Some General Remarks on Struck Copies of
Imperial Bronze Coins of Trajan

by

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A New 'Trajanic' Sestertius from Somerset and its Context: Some General Remarks on Struck Copies of Imperial Bronze Coins of Trajan¹

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PLATES 7-10

IN NOVEMBER 2009, a sestertius with Trajan's portrait and legends resembling the inscriptions of this emperor's well-known 'SPQR OPTIMO PRINCIPI' group of COS V bronzes (AD 103–11)² was reported to Anna Booth, the Portable Antiquities Scheme's Finds Liaison Officer in Somerset (**Pl. 7, 1-1a**). This coin, which is said to have been found in Somerset about ten years ago, differs from all previously recorded Trajan sestertii in having no design at all on the reverse apart from a large SC; it was therefore initially considered to represent a new Trajanic coin type and communicated to the author of this contribution.

Obv. IMP CAES NERVAE IRAIANO AVG GER DAC P M TR P COS V P P
Laureate bust of Trajan r., drapery on left shoulder.
Dotted border. Dimple in the centre beneath Trajan's ear.

Rev. SPQR [OPTI]MO PRINCIPI
S C
Dotted border. Struck slightly off centre.

Weight 20.6g; axis 6h; diameter 30.94 mm

Portable Antiquities Scheme (PAS), Find no. SOM-E7EDD7

Inter alia, the error in the obverse legend, the unusual dimple below Trajan's ear and the somewhat austere portrait style show that this is not an official sestertius of a hitherto unknown type produced in Rome, but a barbarous copy, albeit one of unusually good workmanship and considerable artistic quality. During the protracted phase of preparation of new systematic catalogues of Trajan's imperial coinages

¹ Thanks are due to Richard Abdy and Sam Moorhead for directing my attention to the newly found coin as well as to Markus Peter, whose comments on an earlier version of this paper were invaluable. I would also like to thank Edward Besly for providing bibliographical information and several scans of coins kept in the National Museum of Wales, Frank L. Kovacs for sending me photographs of an important comparative piece in a private collection, Kay Ehling (Munich Coin Cabinet), and Bernhard Weisser (Berlin Coin Cabinet). Furthermore, I am very grateful to the curatorial staff of the American Numismatic Society (New York) and in particular Rick Witschonke: the final version of this paper was prepared during the 2010 Eric P. Newman Graduate Seminar of the ANS, in which I participated as Visiting Scholar in Residence.

² *RIC* 459–589.

for the series *MIR* and *RIC*,³ information on numerous contemporary imitations typologically related to the official Trajanic material has been collected, both from public and private collections as well as from the international coin trade. Such pieces, which are known in all three metals, exhibit a bewildering variety of styles and were manufactured with diverse production techniques. Fortunately, among the coins in my files there are several which help to elucidate the context in which the newly discovered piece was produced. Since reference books on imperial coinages are not the best place to discuss related imitations in greater detail, it seems fitting to present here some of the more important groups of struck imitations of Trajanic bronzes which have been registered so far.

Unofficial imitations of Roman coins, frequently unattractive and notoriously difficult to classify, have in the past all too often been neglected.⁴ Recently, this trend has been reversed, and scholarly interest in this vast class of coinage is steadily growing, as has been observed in the current *Survey*.⁵ Nevertheless, surprisingly little has been written so far on struck imitations of bronze coins of the Adoptive Emperors. This may be due to the fact that, chronologically, these pieces fall outside the large-scale epidemics of bronze coin copying in the Principate: these occurred in the mid first century AD as well as in the late second/early third centuries,⁶ and currently receive more attention. For example, the numerous imitations of bronzes of Claudius I were surveyed recently.⁷ Furthermore, cast bronzes from the Danubian limes (the so-called ‘*Limesfalsa*’) and a peculiar class of struck copper-plated coins with an iron core from the same region were subjected to an exhaustive systematic treatment just three years ago;⁸ the ‘*Limesfalsa*’ produced from Trajanic originals are

³ B. Woytek, Die Reichsprägung des Kaisers Traianus (98–117). *Moneta Imperii Romani* 14. 2 vols (Vienna, 2010). The sections covering Nerva and Trajan in the second edition of *RIC* vol. II.2 are currently in preparation.

⁴ A good general introduction to these coins, accompanied by a most useful bibliography, is provided by C. King, ‘Roman copies’, in C.E. King and D.G. Wigg (eds), *Coin Finds and Coin Use in the Roman World. The Thirteenth Oxford Symposium on Coinage and Monetary History*, 25.–27. 3. 1993. A NATO Advanced Research Workshop. SFMA 10 (Berlin, 1996), pp. 237–63.

⁵ M. Peter, ‘Imitations of Roman Coins’, in M. Amandry and D. Bateson (eds), *A Survey of Numismatic Research 2002–2007*. IAPN SP 15 (Glasgow, 2009), pp. 196–9, at 196.

⁶ See King, ‘Roman copies’, pp. 239f., and M. Peter, ‘Imitation und Fälschung in römischer Zeit’, in A.-F. Auberson, H.R. Derschka and S. Frey-Kupper (eds), *Faux – contrefaçons – imitations. Actes du quatrième colloque international du Groupe suisse pour l’étude des trouvailles monétaires (Martigny, 1er – 2 mars 2002)*. Études de numismatique et d’histoire monétaire 5 (Lausanne, 2004), pp. 19–30, esp. 22–4.

⁷ P.-A. Besombes, ‘Le monnayage d’imitation de bronze de Claude I^{er}: fraude et non nécessité’, in Auberson, Derschka and Frey-Kupper, *Faux – contrefaçons – imitations*, pp. 31–41; see also Philip Harper, ‘Stylistic links among copies of bronze coins of Claudius I found in Britain and in Spain’ in the present volume.

⁸ M. Pfisterer, ‘Limesfalsa und Eisenmünzen. Römischer Ersatzkleingeld am Donaulimes’, in M. Alram and F. Schmidt-Dick (eds), *Numismata Carnuntina. Forschungen und Material (FMRÖ Abteilung III: Niederösterreich. Band 2: Die antiken Fundmünzen im Museum Carnuntinum)*, 3 vols (Vienna, 2007), pp. 643–875.

conveniently catalogued there.⁹ Struck imitations of Trajan's denarii, often plated,¹⁰ have also occasionally been studied in the past several decades,¹¹ but there is hardly any specialized literature on struck copies of his bronzes.

Heinrich Schürmann (†1979), who assembled the best collection of imperial and provincial coins of Trajan, numbering some 3,500 pieces,¹² published just two unusual struck imitations from his holdings,¹³ and Daniel Nony presented a most interesting imitative sestertius of Trajan kept in the 'médaillier municipal' of Limoges in a short note¹⁴ (we shall come back to this piece below). Apart from these two papers, one has to turn to the summary commentary on barbarous copies provided by Paul L. Strack, who also lists and illustrates several imitative bronzes,¹⁵ and, most importantly, to the catalogue of the Trajanic holdings of the Bibliothèque Nationale in Paris.¹⁶ The latter volume features the most extensive section on contemporary copies of all the museum catalogues available.¹⁷ In all the other published collections, there is just the odd struck imitative bronze of Trajan: see, for example, the catalogues of London,¹⁸ Glasgow,¹⁹ Princeton²⁰ or Grenoble.²¹ Finally, some struck barbarous bronzes with Trajanic types can be found in publications dealing with larger groups of Roman coins

⁹ Pfisterer, 'Limesfalsa', pp. 782–4 (catalogue: nos. 47–61); plates 85–6.

¹⁰ For the different classes of imitations of Roman denarii, see M. Peter, 'Imitations of Roman coins in non-Roman contexts: some remarks', in A. Bursche, R. Ciolek and R. Wolters (eds), *Roman Coins outside the Empire. Ways and Phases, Contexts and Functions. Proceedings of the ESF/SCH Exploratory Workshop Radziwiłł Palace, Nieborów (Poland), 3-6 September 2005*. Collection Moneta 82 (Wetteren, 2008), pp. 389–94, esp. 390–2.

¹¹ See, for example, E. Milliau, 'Denier hybride de Trajan trouvé à Liberchies', *CENB* 1, no. 2 (July 1964), p. 28; L. Chaurand, 'Imitation barbare d'un denier de Trajan', *BSFN* 25, no. 2 (February 1970), p. 498; I. Winkler, 'Der dritte Traians-Denar mit PAT statt PAX', *JNG* 20 (1970), pp. 79–80; J. Radstaat, 'Drie imitaties van denarii van Trajanus', *De Beeldenaar* 5, no. 2 (March/April 1981), pp. 50–1; D.O.A. Klose, 'Zwei seltene römische Fundmünzen aus dem Landkreis Saarlouis im Saarland', *JNG* 46 (1996), pp. 73–6, esp. 73–4.

¹² See J.P.A. van der Vin, 'De Dr. Schürmann-collectie als bruikleen in het Koninklijke Penningkabinet', *De Beeldenaar* 5, no. 2 (March/April 1981), pp. 49–50. The collection is now in the Geldmuseum, Utrecht.

¹³ H. Schürmann, 'Onbekende Trajanus-munten', *JMP* 38 (1951), pp. 101–3.

¹⁴ D. Nony, 'Sesterce d'imitation de Trajan', *BSFN* 35, no. 7 (July 1980), pp. 737–8.

¹⁵ P.L. Strack, *Untersuchungen zur römischen Reichsprägung des zweiten Jahrhunderts. Teil I: Die Reichsprägung zur Zeit des Traian* (Stuttgart, 1931), esp. 'Anhang II. A. Barbarische Nachprägungen und fehlerhafte Münzen', pp. 292–4, with some illustrations on pl. IX.

¹⁶ P.-A. Besombes, [Bibliothèque nationale de France.] *Monnaies de l'Empire romain IV. Trajan (98–117 après J.-C.)* (Paris/Strasbourg, 2008). On this, see also my review article 'Trajan dans les collections de la BnF', *RN* 165 (2009), pp. 427–41.

¹⁷ Besombes, *Trajan*, pp. 117–20, as well as pl. 54–5 (for the bronzes, see nos. 1000–16).

¹⁸ *BMCRE* 3, Trajan nos. 722, 890 and 1079.

¹⁹ A.S. Robertson, *Roman Imperial Coins in the Hunter Coin Cabinet, University of Glasgow. Vol. 2: Trajan to Commodus* (London/Glasgow/New York, 1971), no. 212.

²⁰ B.E. Levy and P.C.V. Bastien, *Roman Coins in the Princeton University Library. I: Republic to Commodus* (Wetteren, 1985), no. 1362.

²¹ B. Rémy, P.-A. Besombes, C. Delattre and M. Amandry, *Grenoble, Bibliothèque Municipale d'Étude et d'Information. Catalogue des monnaies. II: Monnaies romaines. Monnaies impériales romaines 4. Trajan*, *Materiali Studi Ricerche* 22 (Milan, 2001), no. 313.

unearthed in France.²² Paul-André Besombes provided a listing of all the imitative struck bronzes copying Trajanic coins known to him, which totals 70 pieces.²³ He did not, however, add any significant comment or illustrate his (incomplete) list with a substantial number of coins from collections other than the one he published. In summary, no comprehensive approach to this difficult material has been attempted so far.

Without doubt, the reason for this is that struck copies form an extremely heterogeneous body of material, and after decades of evidence-collection many of the pieces remain isolated. However, once a critical mass of data has been compiled, it becomes possible to link at least some coins in die chains and style groups, and thus to partly reconstruct the production. This is the case with the newly found sestertius from Somerset. This piece was struck from the same obverse die used to produce an imitative sestertius offered in 1993 by Classical Numismatic Group (incorporating Seaby Coins), in a list also featuring a special ‘collection of coins relating to Roman Britain’.²⁴ The CNG coin is now in a private collection in the US (**PI. 7, 2-2a**).²⁵

Obv. [IMP CAES NERV]AE IRAIANO AVG GER DAC [P M TR P COS V P P]
Laureate bust of Trajan r., drapery on left shoulder.

Dotted border.

Die break across the neck.

Rev. SDOP OPTIMO PPINDIPI (retrograde; legend starting at 4 o'clock)
S C (in left and right field)

Rectangular *modius* with corn ears. Exergual line.

Dotted border; dots mostly linked to form line.

Weight 25.01g; axis unknown; diameter 32.5 mm

Incontrovertible evidence that the obverse die is the same is provided by the large die break on the piece in the private collection, which must have been struck later than the Somerset sestertius published here for the first time. On the PAS coin, one can discern the first signs of the damage between the A of ‘ANO’ in the legend and the loop of the laurel wreath’s ties, as well as at the emperor’s neck. It is most

²² See R. Étienne, M. Rachet et al., *Le trésor de Garonne. Essai sur la circulation monétaire en Aquitaine à la fin du règne d’Antonin le Pieux (159–161)* (Bordeaux, 1984), nos. 914, 972 and 1036 (pl. XVI: three sestertii from the same obverse die); P.H. Mitard, ‘Les monnaies du sanctuaire gallo-romain des «Vaux-de-la-Celle» à Genainville (Val-d’Oise)’, *TM* 15 (1995), pp. 169–213, nos. 51, 52, 96 and 498 (all illustrated on pl. XIX); P.-A. Besombes, ‘Le dépôt monétaire de 22 438 monnaies du gué de Saint-Léonard (commune de Mayenne)’, *TM* 21 (2003/2004), pp. 1–189, nos. 22136–22146 (struck imitations; all illustrated on pl. 41).

²³ Besombes, *Trajan*, p. 28. This listing comprises not only published specimens, but also pieces quoted from ‘données Besombes’ (*vel sim.*) without further information.

²⁴ *Classical Numismatic Review* 18, no. 2 (1993), no. 203. For the contents of the list, see the editorial, p. 1; the ‘British’ collection, particularly strong in pieces of Carausius and Allectus, was offered as nos. 1–90.

²⁵ I am particularly grateful to the coin’s owner and to Frank L. Kovacs for providing digital images of the sestertius.

surprising to see this die of excellent style²⁶ coupled with a crude reverse bearing a retrograde legend. This reverse die is also found in combination with another obverse, which was perhaps introduced when the damaged obverse had become completely unusable. This third die combination is represented by a sestertius offered by Frank L. Kovacs in his undated Fixed Price List 29, no. 57 (**Pl. 7, 3**).

Obv. IMP CAES NERVAE TRAIANO AVG G[
(reading uncertain due to the condition of the coin and the quality of the illustration available)
Laureate bust of Trajan r., drapery on left shoulder.
Dotted border. Dimple in the centre beneath Trajan's ear?

Rev. SDOP OPTIMO PPINDIPI (retrograde; legend starting at 4 o'clock)
S C (in left and right field)
Rectangular *modius* with corn ears. Exergual line.
Dotted border; dots mostly linked to form line.

Weight 27.14g; axis unknown; diameter 33 mm

The portrait on this coin is also of high quality, but the two obverses of the group can easily be distinguished, since the truncation of the bust and the shape of the drapery are completely different, as is the form of the wreath ties. As for production technique, the new sestertius from Somerset and the piece offered by Kovacs are probably connected by the small circular dimple at the centre of their obverses.²⁷ This feature occurs regularly on Ptolemaic and Seleucid bronzes as well as on Roman provincial coins from the Balkans and from Asia Minor,²⁸ where it is especially frequent from the second half of the 2nd century AD onward. Its occurrence on a barbarous imitation is somewhat surprising; to the best of my knowledge, there are no secure parallels on imitative bronze coins of the Principate.²⁹ The precise purpose of these dimples, which were applied to the flans prior to striking, is still debated. It seems clear, however, that their purpose must have been purely technical, doubtless

²⁶ It was therefore erroneously identified as an 'official die' by the CNG cataloguer.

²⁷ On the PAS coin the dimple is clear. For the sestertius in trade we cannot be absolutely sure, due to the relatively poor quality of the image available, although it seems quite likely to me that the small depression right in the centre of the flan is a dimple as well.

²⁸ The most recent comprehensive treatment of the phenomenon is provided by B. Bouyon, G. Depeyrot and J.-L. Desnier, *Systèmes et technologie des monnaies de bronze (4^e s. avant J.-C. – 3^e s. après J.-C.)*. Collection Moneta 19 (Wetteren, 2000), esp. pp. 14–28 and 77f. (Ptolemies) and 79–89 (Roman provincial coins).

²⁹ An imitative as copying Domitianic types which was found in Augusta Raurica, Switzerland (local museum Inv. 77.15838; 11.18g, 7h) shows a depression on the obverse, but because of its irregular shape it is not entirely clear whether it is really a dimple of the type under discussion. See also Besombes, 'gué de Saint-Léonard', no. 22139 (5.92g; pl. 41, illustrated from a cast: uncertain depressions in the centre of the coin on both obverse and reverse).

connected with the preparation of the blanks.³⁰ Explanations connecting the feature with the circulation of the coins are not convincing.³¹

The prototype of our group's second reverse die was probably the *modius* with corn ears and a poppy from Nerva's famous PLEBEI VRBANAE FRUMENTO CONSTITVTO sestertii, struck in AD 97 (Pl. 8, 4).³² It may be noted that this reverse type was relatively easy to copy due to the shape of the *modius* – probably a deliberate choice by the die cutter, who obviously had problems with mirror-inverted engraving, as the legend on the die testifies. As for the prototype of the new sestertius with the large S C, different hypotheses may be put forward. It is not unlikely that its reverse design, with the two main letters so far apart, was the result of a premature termination of the engraving process of the die. The die cutter simply could have stopped before adding a central design, and the die was immediately used at this stage. If, however, the design as it appears today was meant to copy an official Roman prototype, it need not necessarily derive from Augustan or Tiberian sestertii, which frequently have an SC as their only reverse type. It may well have been modelled on another coin type of Nerva, viz. his DIVVS AVGVSTVS sestertii (Pl. 8, 5).³³ According to Komnick, this is the most frequently occurring restored coin type of the High Principate in general,³⁴ and it is much more common than Nerva's sestertii with the *modius*. In the coin circulation of the beginning of the second century AD, these pieces were probably more common than sestertii of the early principate, so that it is conceivable that their reverse was copied on the Somerset imitation.

³⁰ See, for example, K. Butcher, *Roman Provincial Coins. An Introduction to the 'Greek Imperials'* (London, 1988), p. 67: 'possibly the result of [sc. the coin] being clamped in a sort of lathe device used to smoothe off the edges of the coin' and, *contra*, H.E. Wagner, 'Das zentrale Bohrloch auf antiken Bronzen', *Helvetische Münzenzeitung* 34, no. 5 (May 1999), pp. 269–73, esp. 271: 'Das Zentralloch wurde beim Glätten der Oberfläche der gegossenen Schrötlinge mittels eines fräserartigen Bohrers erzeugt.'. To me, Wagner's suggestion seems preferable. See also J. Guey and M. Picon, 'Quelques remarques sur la fabrication des grands bronzes lagides à cavités centrales', *BSFN* 23, no. 2 (February 1968), pp. 240–1; M. Picon and J. Guey, 'Monnaies frappées sur des flans tournés ne présentant pas de cavités centrales', *BSFN* 23, no. 10 (December 1968), pp. 336–7; H. Bartlett Wells, 'Tooled surfaces for copper flans of large «Greek Imperial» coins', *SM* 38, no. 150 (May 1988), pp. 41–5. M. Bahrfieldt, *Antike Münztechnik* (Berlin, 1903: "Sonder-Abdruck aus 'Berliner Münzblätter N. F.' 1904, No. 25"), pp. 16–8, and F. Leypold, 'Das Problem „Zentrierloch“', *MÖNG* 36, no. 1 (1996), pp. 6–8, and 'Nochmals zum Problem „Zentrierloch“', *MÖNG* 37, no. 4 (1997), pp. 87–8, miss the point.

³¹ According to Bouyon et al., *Systèmes et technologie*, pp. 87–9, the dimple in the centre always served to distinguish two different classes of coins in circulation: in Roman times, they believe the feature to have been introduced in order to differentiate provincial from imperial bronze issues. This does not seem at all likely, since so few imperial bronzes circulated, *e. g.*, in Asia Minor.

³² *RIC* 89 and 103.

³³ *RIC* 136.

³⁴ H. Komnick, *Die Restitutionsmünzen der frühen Kaiserzeit. Aspekte der Kaiserlegitimation* (Berlin/New York, 2001), type Nerva 4.0: see pp. 101, 144f. and 231–3 (more than 100 specimens from at least 32 obverse dies known to Komnick). The type is thus significantly more common than the restored sestertii of Titus featuring a large SC on the reverse, for which see Komnick nos. 1–3, 6, 9 and 13; moreover, these pieces have not only a legend around the SC, but also the additional letters REST above, so that the 'Architektonik des Münzbildes' (R. Göbl, *Antike Numismatik*, 2 vols (Munich, 1978), vol. 2, pp. 232f. and pl. 131) does not correspond to the reverse of the Trajanic imitation published here.

It is by no means unusual to find, in a group of bronze imitations of the High Principate, one obverse die linked to two reverses with different images. Another example, from the Trajanic material available to me, is provided by what one might call a 'Fortuna group'. A sestertius in the Schürmann collection showing Fortuna standing left (with rudder and *cornucopiae*) on the reverse³⁵ (Pl. 8, 6) was struck from the same obverse die as a sestertius now in Paris featuring the deity with the same attributes seated to the left, with FORT RED and SC in the exergue (Pl. 8, 7).³⁶ To this pair should be added a sestertius in Munich, listed but not illustrated by Strack³⁷ and Bernhart³⁸ (Pl. 8, 8). It too shows a seated FORTuna REDux (just the SC is missing here), and although this piece comes from a different pair of dies, it is closely linked stylistically to the two other coins and its dies were doubtless cut by the same engraver; it cannot be a product of the Roman mint, as erroneously surmised by Strack.³⁹

But let us return to the Trajanic 'SC and *modius*' group, about which two things are particularly interesting: the typological combinations it shows, and the retrograde legend on one of the reverse dies. Let us consider both of these features in greater detail.

First, these coins seem to be Nerva/Trajan hybrids, typologically speaking. In the majority of cases, struck imitations of Trajanic coins copy the types of the originals more or less faithfully on both obverse and reverse: see, for example, the sestertii with Concordia (Pl. 8, 9: copying *MIR* 21), with Pax and kneeling Dacian (Pl. 9, 10: copying *MIR* 247–1⁴⁰), or with Annona between *modius* and ship (Pl. 9, 11: copying *MIR* 323–2). Sometimes the reverse image was slightly altered, but generally the lineage from the prototype remains more than evident. For example, on the coin at Pl. 9, 12, a sestertius with impeccable legends copied from the large COS V issue of aes, Annona is still easily recognizable, although ship and *modius* were left out and the corn ears in the deity's right hand were stylized to the form of a triangle. The barbarous coin in the Schürmann collection at Pl. 9, 13 which shows Victory

³⁵ Schürmann coll., inv. no. 2511. This was one of the pieces published by the collector himself: Schürmann, 'Onbekende Trajanus-munten', p. 101f. (with accurate description), no. 1 (illustrated on Schürmann's pl. VI). Provenance unknown.

³⁶ Besombes, *Trajan*, no. 1001 (acquired from P.-F. Jacquier in 1997: FPL 19, no. 468); die-link noted.

³⁷ Strack, *Reichsprägung*, p. 293, no. 6.

³⁸ M. Bernhart, *Die Münzen der römischen Kaiserzeit* (Munich, no date), p. 322, no. 340 (legends partly misread). According to a publisher's pamphlet known to me, this book was to appear in print in about 1944 with the title *Korpus der römischen Kaisermünzen*, but it remained unfinished and unpublished due to the war; the signatures and plates which had already been printed and had survived the war were re-discovered and published in 2003.

³⁹ Strack, *Reichsprägung*, p. 293: 'Der Fehler liegt hier nur in der Legende, die Bildstempel sind beide gut und stammen aus der römischen Officin.'

⁴⁰ On this imitation, Pax holds a *cornucopiae* in her left hand, an attribute not present on the prototype.

with a shield reading ‘VIC / DAC’ on the reverse is a case of its own.⁴¹ On the prototype (*MIR* 204) the goddess stands to the right, but on the copy she is seated on a throne, and, curiously enough, three minute human-like figures have been added in the exergue.⁴²

The prototypes of all the coins cited so far were bronzes,⁴³ but in a few instances the metal was switched for the copies, as already noted by Daniel Nony.⁴⁴ He published an imitative sestertius from a collection in Limoges with Trajan’s portrait and Victory seated left on a throne, holding *patera* and palm branch – a reverse type never used on Trajan’s *aes*, but only on his precious metal coins. A rather worn sestertius at present kept in Utrecht’s *Geldmuseum*, illustrated here at **Pl. 9, 14**, is from the same reverse die (and indeed, most probably, even from the same die pair) as the coin published by Nony. What can be read of its reverse legend (PONT MAX) confirms Nony’s reading and therefore his contention that the design was copied from a Trajanic precious metal coin of the COS II period, since these abbreviations occur exclusively on gold and silver of AD 98, never on bronze.⁴⁵ Contrary to Nony’s belief, however, the half aureus with this reverse can hardly have served as the prototype of the imitative sestertii, since it was produced in exiguous quantities and today is known in only one example.⁴⁶ It must have been the common denarius of this type that was copied (*MIR* 38). Similarly, the images of the sestertius at **Pl. 9, 15** were inspired by Trajanic denarii. Its obverse legend IMP CAES NERVA TRAIAN AVG GERM was the classic obverse legend for precious metal coins of Trajan from AD 98 to 103, and the reverse type, Pax standing to the left with branch and *cornucopiae*, was exclusively used on denarii under this emperor. On the early Pax denarii, whose P M TR P COS... inscription seems to be echoed in the garbled reverse legend of this imitative sestertius, Pax always holds the branch upwards,⁴⁷ but her gesture on the bronze certainly reflects the pose of Felicitas on the Trajanic denarii *MIR* 280. On these silver pieces, due to careless engraving, the *caduceus* often resembles a branch, and the personification was therefore mistaken for Pax even by some modern numismatists.⁴⁸ The reverse design as such was ‘adapted’

⁴¹ Schürmann coll., inv. no. 2513. It was first published by A. Banti, *I grandi bronzi imperiali. Nerva – Traianus. Plotina – Marciana – Matidia. Selezione di sesterzi e medaglioni classificati secondo il sistema Cohen* (Florence, 1983), p. 121, no. 171/A. This coin is also illustrated by Besombes, *Trajan*, pl. I, no. 7. Its legends are nearly ‘correct’: IMP CAES NERVA TRAIANO AVG GER DAC P M TR P COS V P P / SPQR OPTIMO [...]*JNCIPI*, S–C.

⁴² One in the centre is being crowned (?) by a figure on the right, while a (winged?) figure on the left seems to be seated.

⁴³ Most probably, sestertii were copied from sestertii, although this cannot be proved for the coins cited in this paragraph, since all the reverses concerned were also struck on dupondii and asses.

⁴⁴ ‘Sesterce d’imitation’, pp. 737f.

⁴⁵ The obverse legend of the prototype was IMP CAES NERVA TRAIAN AVG GERM, and the sestertius in Utrecht reads] CAES NERVA TRAIAN AVG [. The obverse legend of the Limoges piece was read as IMP CAES NERVA ... AVG GERM by Nony, so that the entire legend can be reconstructed from the two coins. On the reverse, where the prototype’s legend is PONT MAX TR POT COS II, the letters SC were added in the exergue of the sestertius die.

⁴⁶ *BMCRE* 3, Trajan 20: *MIR* 37.

⁴⁷ *MIR* 57, 75 and 106.

⁴⁸ See, for example, Strack, *Reichsprägung*, description of no. 134.

for use on a bronze imitation by the local workman adding the letters D – D in the fields, which are doubtless to be interpreted as a deformation of the SC formula.⁴⁹ In any case, both in **Pl. 9, 14** and **15**, the two sides of the coins were each copied from Trajanic prototypes. The change in dimensions from the prototype to the copy which is evident in these coins nicely highlights a general technical feature of the imitative bronzes considered here. As far as I can see, they were normally all struck from dies engraved freehand, not from dies reproduced mechanically, as was the case with some other classes of Roman imitative coinages.⁵⁰

Apart from the coins of the newly discovered 'SC and *modius*' group, there are hardly any imitative sestertii in my files which are typological hybrids combining Trajanic designs with those of another emperor. One notable exception is a piece in the Berlin Coin Cabinet (**Pl. 9, 16**). Its obverse shows Trajan's draped portrait bust and a TRAIANO OPTIMO legend of the period AD 114–6, whereas the reverse type is Virtus standing left, with *parazonium* and spear, and her right foot on a helmet – not a Trajanic bronze type at all. The VIRT – AVG legend in the left and right field, above the S – C, together with the legible beginning of the round legend 'P M ...', makes it clear that this side of the coin was copied from sestertii of Hadrian.⁵¹ Particular problems are posed by two Libertas sestertii bearing Trajan's portrait (**Pl. 10, 17–18**).

Obv. IMP CAES NERVA TRAIAN – AVG GERM P M

Laureate head of Trajan right. Dotted border.

Rev. LIBERTAS – PVBLICA

S – C in left and right field

Libertas standing left, holding *pileus* and short double rod.

Dotted border.

Utrecht, Schürmann collection, inv. no. 1488 (**Pl. 10, 17**).

Weight 26.33g; axis 6h

Obv. IMP CAES NERVA TRAIAN – N AVG GERMA

Laureate head of Trajan right. Dotted border.

Die break across Trajan's neck.

Rev. LIBERTAS – PVBLICA

S – C in left and right field

Libertas standing left, holding *pileus* and short double rod.

Dotted border.

Several die flaws.

Kunst und Münzen AG 29 (20 May 1993), no. 280 (**Pl. 10, 18**).

Technical data unknown.

⁴⁹ Whether the formula *D(ecreto) D(ecurionum)*, so frequent in provincial inscriptions, had an influence on this coin legend is not clear.

⁵⁰ Such dies were used for some imitative denarii or for bronzes with an iron core: see Pfisterer, 'Limesfalsa', pp. 740–3, and M. Pfisterer and R. Traum, 'Die Herstellungstechnik subferrater Kopien römischer Buntmetallmünzen: ein praktisches Experiment', *SNR* 84 (2005), pp. 125–40.

⁵¹ *RIC* 614.

These pieces were struck from the same reverse die, but from two different obverse dies. The Schürmann coin was produced first, since the reverse die was in much better condition when this sestertius was struck;⁵² in general, there seem to have been serious problems with the quality of the dies used for these coins, since the obverse die attested on the piece auctioned in 1993 exhibits severe damage as well. In style as well as in fabric, these pieces (which currently do not have a patina) are unlike any other struck copies of Trajanic bronzes known to me,⁵³ and the possibility that they are products of modern times cannot be ruled out completely, although this seems rather unlikely.⁵⁴ In any case, the coins are typological hybrids: LIBERTAS PVBLICA, standing left with *pileus* and sceptre, is one of the classic reverses of Nerva.⁵⁵ Under Hadrian, the same personification occurs on sestertii with the same legend, although here her secondary attribute is a branch, not a sceptre.⁵⁶ Since the strange double rod on our imitations is an object invented by the die-cutter, it is not immediately obvious whose Libertas sestertii were copied here, but on balance, it seems more plausible that it was Nerva's.

The second peculiarity of the typologically hybrid 'SC and *modius*' group is the retrograde, somewhat blundered SPQR OPTIMO PRINCIPI legend on one of the dies. Retrograde legends in general hardly ever occur on the Trajanic copies known to me. An exception is a barbarous dupondius with Abundantia/Securitas (the characteristic reverse of this denomination in the first phase of Trajan's rule), first published by Schürmann,⁵⁷ which has a partly retrograde reverse legend (Pl. 10, 19): TR POT on the left in mirror writing, but COS IIII P P on the right written correctly.

The only other coins on which the entire reverse legend is retrograde – just as on the *modius* die of the production batch reconstructed here – are middle bronzes of the so-called 'Caerleon-Caerwent group' of Romano-British copies. This substantial group of die-struck orichalcum copies was first identified and discussed by George C. Boon in the late 1960s,⁵⁸ and several new pieces belonging to it have emerged since. In 1984, John P. Goddard published one new coin,⁵⁹ and in his groundbreaking 1988 paper Boon reported further specimens and provided a short general commentary on the series.⁶⁰ Some of these coins are Nerva/Trajan hybrids, combining Nerva obverses with reverses inscribed SPQR OPTIMO PRINCIPI. Two different reverse types of

⁵² See, for example, the die break beneath the right arm of Libertas.

⁵³ In Utrecht, the sestertius was classified as a regular coin of a hitherto unknown type.

⁵⁴ Thanks are due to Markus Peter and Matthias Pfisterer for discussing these pieces with me.

⁵⁵ Nerva's sestertii: *RIC* 64, 76, 86.

⁵⁶ *RIC* 584.

⁵⁷ Schürmann, 'Onbekende Trajanus-munten', p. 102, no. 2 (illustrated on Schürmann's pl. VI). Schürmann coll., inv. no. 2509; provenance unknown.

⁵⁸ G.C. Boon, 'Die linked counterfeits from Caerwent and Caerleon', *The Monmouthshire Antiquary* 2 (1965–8), pp. 52–5, and 'Another die-linked counterfeit', *The Monmouthshire Antiquary* 2 (1965–8), p. 119.

⁵⁹ J.P. Goddard, 'A Nerva/Trajan hybrid. Another example of the "Caerleon-Caerwent group" of Romano-British copies', *NCirc* 92, no. 3 (April 1984), p. 76.

⁶⁰ G.C. Boon, 'Counterfeit coins in Roman Britain', in J. Casey and R. Reece (eds), *Coins and the Archaeologist*. Second edition (London, 1988), pp. 102–88, at p. 110f. with n. 48 (p. 152) and p. 179; illustrations on pl. II, nos. 25–7.

this kind have been recorded so far. The coin published by Goddard (**Pl. 10, 20**) has Trajan on a horse prancing right, brandishing a javelin at a Dacian fallen beneath the horse, a reverse copied from the bronzes *MIR* 317–9 (c. AD 107–9). On this piece the legend is orthodox, but it is retrograde on another reverse die, displaying *Spes* walking left (**Pl. 10, 21**).⁶¹ Theoretically, this depiction of *Spes* could of course have been inspired by earlier imperial coins, but its combination with the *SPQR OPTIMO PRINCIPI* legend makes it likely that it was copied from the Trajan bronzes with this personification (*MIR* 338–40). Since these coins were struck in Rome only in c. AD 109/110, according to my new chronology of Trajan's bronzes, the date proposed by Boon for the 'Caerleon-Caerwent group' of copies – 'immediately after [...] 103'⁶² – must be too early.

These coins circulated mainly in the south-west of Britain, with a particular concentration of find spots in South Wales, north of the Bristol Channel.⁶³ This area is close to Somerset, where the new SC sestertius was discovered. For the two *modius* sestertii from trade, we unfortunately do not know provenances, although the 'Romano-British' context in which the CNG/Seaby piece (**Pl. 7, 2**) was offered might prompt speculation that this is a British site find as well. On balance, it seems likely to me that the 'SC and *modius*' group of imitative sestertii was also produced in Roman Britain.⁶⁴ The similarities of these large bronzes to the 'Caerleon-Caerwent group' of middle bronzes, namely the hybrid linkage of Nerva and Trajan types and the otherwise unattested use of a retrograde *SPQR OPTIMO PRINCIPI* legend, seem quite telling. Nevertheless, we cannot be sure that both groups of imitations originated in the same coin-producing environment, for stylistically the pieces do not have much in common, except for the protruding emperor's forehead in **Pl. 7, 1–2** and **Pl. 10, 21–2**; the middle bronzes also lack the dimple in the centre.

Recently, the function of imitative coinages in the Roman world – and especially of struck copies of bronze coins – has been the focus of scholarly debate.⁶⁵ There has been considerable disagreement as to whether these coins should be interpreted as privately produced forgeries, struck exclusively in order to deceive coin users and to generate revenue for the forgers,⁶⁶ or as imitations produced locally in order to circumvent shortages of official small money, and to some extent tolerated by

⁶¹ For this coin type, see Boon, 'Counterfeit coins', pl. II, no. 25. A third reverse type in the group shows *LIBERTAS AVG* (**Pl. 10, 22**).

⁶² Boon, 'Counterfeit coins', p. 111.

⁶³ Examples have been found in Caerleon (2 coins), as well as in Camarthen, Caerwent, Wroxeter, Ffrith near Wrexham and Chichester: see Boon, 'Counterfeit coins', p. 110, who seems to be sceptical as to whether the Chichester coin really belongs to this group (p. 111).

⁶⁴ D.R. Walker, 'The Roman coins', in B. Cunliffe (ed.), *The Temple of Sulis Minerva at Bath, vol. II: Finds from the Sacred Spring* (Oxford, 1988), pp. 281–358, lists only one struck copy of a Trajanic *aes* coin, a sestertius whose reverse is unfortunately illegible (p. 322, no. 3).

⁶⁵ See, for example, several contributions in Auberson, Derschka and Frey-Kupper, *Faux – contrefaçons – imitations* (cited in note 6 above).

⁶⁶ Thus Besombes, 'Claude I^{er}', pp. 34–9.

the government.⁶⁷ The latter view has found more adherents,⁶⁸ and justly so, I think. Additional evidence for the hypothesis that ‘micro-economic’ considerations governed the local production of imitative *aes* coins may perhaps be provided by the Trajanic material itself.

In reviewing the denominational and chronological structure of Trajanic struck copies, Besombes correctly remarked that middle bronzes, dupondii and asses, constitute the largest part of the total of imitative bronzes with Trajanic types which have come down to us. To judge from the dates on the coins, they outnumbered imitative sestertii for all periods of the reign, and often by more than 100%.⁶⁹ In legends of imitative coinages, dates of course do not necessarily indicate the periods when these coins were issued, but merely provide us with a *terminus post quem* for the production of the imitation.⁷⁰ The ‘Trajanic’ imitations therefore need not have been struck under Trajan: they may well have been minted later.⁷¹ But the precise date when these coins were made is not relevant to us here. Whenever they were produced, many more Trajanic middle bronzes than sestertii were imitated, and this fact deserves closer investigation.

Although we have had to concentrate on the sestertius in this contribution (this being the denomination of the new ‘SC and *modius*’ group), sometimes small groups can be isolated within copies of Trajanic middle bronzes as well. A good example are what might be called the ‘Abundantia 3/4/5’ dupondii (see **Pl. 10, 23–5**). An obverse die with a nearly correct COS V legend⁷² is known to me from four coins which all show Abundantia/Securitas seated to the left on crossed *cornuacopiae* on the reverse; she is accompanied by three different inscriptions, characteristic of bronzes of Trajan’s third, fourth and fifth consulates respectively.⁷³ The production of the entire group of dupondii can thus be dated to the COS V period (at the earliest), although the Abundantia reverse was no longer used by the mint in Rome when the SPQR OPTIMO PRINCIPI legend had been introduced.⁷⁴

⁶⁷ This is the opinion of D.G. Wigg-Wolf, ‘Zur Interpretation und Bedeutung der “Barbarisierungen” der römischen Kaiserzeit’, in Auberson, Derschka and Frey-Kupper, *Faux – contrefaçons – imitations*, pp. 55–75, as well as of M. Peter, ‘Imitation und Fälschung’, p. 23, and M. Pfisterer, ‘Falschgeld und Beischläge der Prinzipatszeit in Carnuntum – Ein Überblick’, in Alram and Schmidt-Dick, *Numismata Carnuntina*, pp. 635–42, at 642.

⁶⁸ See also Peter, ‘Imitations’, p. 196.

⁶⁹ Besombes, *Trajan*, p. 28 (listing 39 middle bronzes and 15 sestertii in all).

⁷⁰ See Peter, ‘Imitation und Fälschung’, p. 28.

⁷¹ It may be suspected, however, that in periods of regular production of bronze coins, as under the Adoptive Emperors, the time-lag between the creation of designs by the official mint and their imitation was normally not very great: for people producing imitative pieces, it would have been natural to select current types from freshly minted official coins.

⁷² IMP CAES NERVA TRAIAN AVG GER DAC P M TR P COS V P (P): this die, which seems to have been rather long-lived, was apparently repaired at some stage of the production process and the end of the legend was retouched.

⁷³ The coins of the group known to me so far are: 1. Museum Carnuntinum, published in Alram and Schmidt-Dick, *Numismata Carnuntina*, no. 34344 (11.72g, illustrated in the publication, where it is tentatively classified as a ‘Limesfalsum’); 2. Tietjen 101 (16 June 2008), no. 320 (**Pl. 10, 23**, both coins with TR POT COS III P P, but from different reverse dies); 3. Utrecht, Geldmuseum, general coll. (**Pl. 10, 24**: TR POT COS IIII P P); 4. *BMCRE* 3, Trajan 890 (**Pl. 10, 25**: SPQR OPTIMO PRINCIPI).

⁷⁴ This reverse last appeared on dupondii dated TR P VII IMP IIII COS V P P: *MIR* 154.

On a general level, the numerical importance of imitative middle bronzes of Trajan is in striking contrast to the evidence provided by the official bronze issues of his rule. In circulation, the total of Trajanic sestertii would typically have been higher than the total of his middle bronzes (dupondii and asses together), as may be seen, for example, from the material currently available in the PAS database.⁷⁵ As has been established in recent scholarship, the sestertius took over from the as, as the leading Roman denomination (in quantitative terms), during Trajan's fourth consulate (AD 101–2). At the beginning of his reign, from AD 98–100, asses were struck in Rome in much higher numbers than sestertii, but this ratio was reversed thereafter; in the final phase of Trajanic coin production, the as played just a marginal role, as compared to the sestertius.⁷⁶ This accounts for the overall high percentage of sestertii in populations of official bronze coins.

The reasons for these changes in the Trajanic output remain to be determined. As pointed out above, however, the struck imitations of official bronze coins did not follow this pattern, and 'barbarous' middle bronzes continued to be produced in considerable numbers in Western Europe also with COS V and COS VI dates. Since the pool of potential Trajanic prototypes with these dates was much larger among sestertii than among dupondii or asses, the choice of denomination made by the local people – whenever they produced their imitations – is significant. Thus, the evidence provided by the imitations themselves seems to indicate not fraud strangely concentrated on smaller coins, but a local reaction at some point to the government's failure to send enough bronze coins below sestertius value.⁷⁷ If such coins did not arrive from Rome, the shortage of small change had to be remedied locally.

List of illustrations (all life-size, unless stated otherwise)

- 1 Portable Antiquities Scheme SOM-E7EDD7
- 1a As fig. 1, 200%.
- 2 CNG/Seaby, *Classical Numismatic Review* 18, no. 2 (1993), no. 203 (25.01g).
Private coll.
- 2a As fig. 2, 200%.
- 3 Kovacs FPL 29, no. 57 (27.14g)
- 4 *Ars Classica* 17 (3 October 1934: Sir Arthur Evans), no. 1351 (27.62g)
- 5 UBS 78 (9 September 2008), no. 1381 (29.41g)
- 6 Utrecht, Geldmuseum, Schürmann coll., inv. no. 2511 (24.99g; 6h)

⁷⁵ On 23 June 2010, a database search for Trajanic bronzes produced 416 sestertii and 351 middle bronzes (175 dupondii and 176 asses).

⁷⁶ M. Peter, *Untersuchungen zu den Fundmünzen aus Augst und Kaiseraugst*. SFMA 17 (Berlin, 2001), pp. 98f., and Woytek, *Reichsprägung des Traianus*, pp. 22–4.

⁷⁷ Pace Besombes, 'Claude I^{er}', p. 34–8.

- 7 Paris, Bibliothèque nationale. *BNCMER* 4, no. 1001 (26.41g; 4h)
- 8 Munich, Staatliche Münzsammlung (24.00g; 7h)
- 9 A.S. Robertson, *Roman Imperial Coins in the Hunter Coin Cabinet, University of Glasgow. Vol. 2: Trajan to Commodus* (London etc., 1971), Trajan no. 212 (21.53g; 6h)
- 10 Kunst und Münzen AG 29 (20 May 1993), no. 279
- 11 Utrecht, Geldmuseum, Schürmann coll., inv. no. 2510 (23.78g; 6h)
- 12 Kricheldorf 38 (28 November 1984), no. 647
- 13 Utrecht, Geldmuseum, Schürmann coll., inv. no. 2513 (25.80g; 6h)
- 14 Utrecht, Geldmuseum, general coll.
- 15 Utrecht, Geldmuseum, Schürmann coll., inv. no. 2512 (20.67g; 1h)
- 16 Berlin, Staatliche Museen, Münzkabinett (20.40g; 6h)
- 17 Utrecht, Geldmuseum, Schürmann coll., inv. no. 1488 (26.33g; 6h)
- 18 Kunst und Münzen AG 29 (20 May 1993), no. 280
- 19 Utrecht, Geldmuseum, Schürmann coll., inv. no. 2509 (11.37g; 6h)
- 20 Goddard, 'Nerva/Trajan Hybrid' (see note 59 above), p. 76 (12.64g; 6h)
- 21 National Museum of Wales: Boon, 'Die linked counterfeits' (see note 58 above), p. 52, fig. 2 (11.30g)
- 22 National Museum of Wales: Boon, 'Another die-linked counterfeit' (see note 58 above), not illustrated there (13.40g)
- 23 Tietjen 101 (16 June 2008), no. 320
- 24 Utrecht, Geldmuseum, general coll.
- 25 *BMCRE* 3, Trajan 890 (10.93g; 6h)

1a (2x)

2a (2x)

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PLATE 8

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PLATE 10

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